

ELASTIC MODULUS ESTIMATION OF CHOPPED CARBON FIBER TAPE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS USING THE MONTE CARLO SIMULATION

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1 Introduction

Fig.1 shows energy consumption of transport sector in Japan [1]. It can be seen from this result that in order to solve the energy and environmental problems, it is need to improve fuel efficiency of cars. One of the most effective methods of improving fuel efficiency is reducing weight of production cars using carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP).

However, cars made of CFRP are not almost popular due to high production costs because the molding time of CFRP is long. Therefore, reduction of molding time is essential in order to apply CFRP to production cars. Chopped carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics (CTT) is made from chopped unidirectional CFRTP tapes (UD tapes) which are laid at random (Fig.2). CTT is expected to be applied to complex shaped structural members for production cars and to achieve a high-speed molding and a significant weight reduction of the body structure [2].

However, CTT has a problem in the evaluation of parameters used in CAE caused by the size of the tape. For example, the variation of elastic moduli measured by small specimens is very large (Figs.3-4) though the variation of elastic moduli measured by structural members is sufficiently small (Figs.5-6). When designing a car, the elastic modulus of the material will be as important as the strength. If a car was made from a material having a low elastic modulus, its window will be broken by torsional deformation when it turns the corner, or its doors will not be opened or closed when load is applied to it [3]. Therefore, when a car was made from a material having a high average elastic modulus, but also having a big variation, it is necessary to the thick body because all cars should get the necessary rigidity. So, it is important to measure the correct average elastic modulus and coefficient of variation. On the other hand, because the elastic modulus of the structure of CTT is not varied, we want to put CTT into practical use, but because dimensional

dependency of variation would be large, the development of method to obtain effective material properties required for CAE is necessary.

In this study, we evaluated the elastic modulus of CTT using Monte Carlo method by focusing on the random arrangement of the chopped UD tapes.

2 Problem of the measurement of elastic modulus by tensile test

Standard tensile test method of CTT does not exist yet. Therefore, in order to measure the tensile modulus, we can only use the test conditions of isotropic and orthotropic fiber reinforced plastic which are written to the JIS standard [4]. According to this method, it is recommended that the specimen width is 50 ± 0.5 mm and thickness is 2.0~10 mm, and the distance between the marked lines is 50 ± 1 mm. Also, the number of specimens is more than four. However, this condition might not be appropriate for CTT with the randomness in terms of the size of specimens.

Therefore, in this study, we propose a new model for calculating the elastic modulus of CTT, verify the validity of the model by comparison with experiments with specimens changed thickness or distance between the marked lines, and discuss the test conditions that are suitable for CTT using this model.

3 Modeling and calculated elastic modulus of the CTT specimens

CTT is made from UD tapes approximately 35 mm in length, 15 mm in width, and 0.1 mm in thickness. Therefore, it is considered that in the specimen with a thickness of t mm, $10t$ UD tapes are laminated in the thickness direction like Fig.7. Plane direction is considered to approximate UD tapes to the squares of the same area like Fig.8 and to place the squares

without gaps. And it is considered how much each square is included in the area of the size corresponding to the width of the specimen and the distance between the marked lines.

To make the model of specimen, using the Monte Carlo method, each UD tape is given a direction (θ_i) at random using random number. We calculated the elastic modulus of each square (E_n) by introducing laminate theory in the thickness direction [5]. Equations (1) to (5) are calculation formula of laminate theory and Table1 is the elastic properties of UD tapes which was used when calculating laminate theory.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} C_{11} &= E_1 / (1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}) \\ C_{12} &= \nu_{12}E_2 / (1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}) = \nu_{21}E_1 / (1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}) \\ C_{22} &= E_2 / (1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}) \\ C_{66} &= G_{12} \\ c_i &= \cos \theta_i \\ s_i &= \sin \theta_i \end{aligned} \right\} (1)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \bar{C}_{11i} &= C_{11}c_i^4 + C_{22}s_i^4 + (2C_{12} + 4C_{66})c_i^2s_i^2 \\ \bar{C}_{12i} &= C_{12}(c_i^4 + s_i^4) + (C_{11} + C_{22} - 4C_{66})c_i^2s_i^2 \\ \bar{C}_{22i} &= C_{11}s_i^4 + C_{22}c_i^4 + (2C_{12} + 4C_{66})c_i^2s_i^2 \\ \bar{C}_{16i} &= (C_{11} - C_{12} - 2C_{66})c_i^3s_i - (C_{22} - C_{12} - 2C_{66})c_i s_i^3 \\ \bar{C}_{26i} &= (C_{11} - C_{12} - 2C_{66})c_i s_i^3 - (C_{22} - C_{12} - 2C_{66})c_i^3s_i \\ \bar{C}_{66i} &= (C_{11} + C_{22} - 2C_{12} - 2C_{66})c_i^2s_i^2 + C_{66}(c_i^4 + s_i^4) \end{aligned} \right\} (2)$$

$$C_{xy-t} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{t/0.1} \bar{C}_{xyi}}{t} \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta = C_{11-t}C_{22-t}C_{66-t} + 2C_{12-t}C_{16-t}C_{26-t} - C_{22-t}C_{16-t}^2 - C_{66-t}C_{12-t}^2 - C_{11-t}C_{26-t}^2 \quad (4)$$

$$E_n = \Delta / (C_{22-t}C_{66-t} - C_{26-t}^2) \quad (5)$$

After calculating the elastic modulus of each square, we synthesized the modulus in the width direction (E'_m) by the superposition principle.

$$E'_m = a_1E_1 + a_2E_2 + \dots + a_nE_n \quad (6)$$

After synthesizing the modulus in the width direction, we synthesized the modulus in the longitudinal direction by the superposition principle in order to get the elastic modulus of the measurement range (E).

$$\frac{1}{E} = b_1 \frac{1}{E'_1} + b_2 \frac{1}{E'_2} + \dots + b_m \frac{1}{E'_m} \quad (7)$$

4 Comparison of experimental and calculated results

4.1 Experiment

We obtained the average elastic modulus and coefficient of variation based on standard test conditions of JIS and by performing tensile tests in each of four types of specimens with different thickness (t :mm) and distance between the marked lines (L :mm) and with the same width (W :mm). Table2 shows the conditions of the tensile test specimens. And we calculated average elastic modulus and coefficient of variation using the model based on the same conditions.

The results of these experiments are from Figs.9-12. In Figs.9 and 11, 10 lines are not straight but wave, so it is a question these experimental results are correct. Therefore, we did tensile test of same specimens of W35t2L25 using the contact extensometer (Fig.13). Fig.14 is the result of the tensile test and shows that lines are straight and the slopes of the 10 lines are almost the same as the slopes of the lines of Fig.9, so cause of the waves of the lines in Figs.9 and 11 is using the video extensometer to measure the too small measuring range. Also we found that the waves do not affect measuring the correct value of the elastic modulus.

4.2 Calculation

Figs.15 and 16 show the comparisons of experimental and calculated results. Each blue bar shows the average elastic modulus or coefficient of

variation of the 10 or 6 specimens obtained from the experiment, so each error bar of the blue bar in Fig.15 shows the variation in the elastic modulus of the 10 or 6 specimens. On the other hand, each green bar shows the average of the 1000 averages of the elastic modulus which are obtained by 1000 times simulations of a tensile test of 10 or 6 specimens. The reason that the number of simulations is 1000 times is because it was found from Fig.17 that values are sufficiently converged. Therefore, each error bar of the green bar in Fig.15 shows the variation in the 1000 averages of the elastic modulus of the 10 or 6 specimens and in Fig.16 shows the variation in the 1000 coefficients of variation. Figs.15 and 16 indicate that the model of the Monte Carlo method can represent the experimental results with the exception of the coefficient of variation of W35t2L25. The reason why the difference of calculation results with experimental results of W35t2L25 occurs may be some factors that are not described in this model and become larger when the measurement range is too small. However, this model was found to be applicable enough if the size of the measurement range to be calculated is close to the size of the actual structure or is the size that could be a new test conditions.

5 Influence on the variation of elastic modulus

5.1 Effect of the size and the number of specimen

Fig.18 shows the coefficient of variation when changing L and t . From these results, it can be seen that the coefficient of variation is reduced by increasing t or L . In other words, in CTT, it is important that size of specimen is set so that it doesn't overestimate the variation in the mechanical properties of the actual structure.

Fig.19 shows the comparison of the coefficient of variation of L25t2W25 and the coefficients of variation of the specimen which were doubled each L , t and W . Each coefficient of variation was determined from 10000 specimens. From these results, if specimen is made in the same volume, it should increase the thickness than the width or distance between the marked lines. This is also true from the fact that there is a limit of the specimen size on laboratory instrument.

Fig.20 shows effect of the number of specimens in an experiment. From these results, in the experiment using 10 or more specimens, the average coefficient of variation converges substantially. On the other hand, the standard deviation of the coefficient of

variation decreases as the number of specimens becomes large.

5.2 Effect of cut length of UD tapes

CTT, which has been treated ever, is made of UD tapes which are cut to 35mm, but it is possible to make CTT from UD tapes of varying length to cut. Fig.21 shows comparison of the coefficient of variation of CTT made from UD tapes with different cut length. From these results, it can be seen that the shorter the cut length of UD tapes is, the smaller the variation of the elastic modulus is. So, in the future, we will verify the effect of the cut length in the experiment.

6 Conclusion

The proposed model using laminate theory and the Monte Carlo method were successfully able to represent the elastic modulus and their variation of tensile CTT specimens.

It was found that the variation of the elastic modulus depends on the size of specimen. Therefore, this model enable us to find reasonable test conditions to evaluate an intrinsic elastic modulus and its variation of CTT.

Fig.1 Energy consumption of transport sector in Japan

Fig.2 Chopped carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics (CTT).

Fig.5 Three-point bending test.

Fig.3 Tensile test using the video extensometer.

Fig.6 Results of three-point bending test using large frame members.

Fig.4 Results of the tensile test using small specimens.

Fig.7 Modeling method of thickness.

Fig.8 Modeling method of width and distance between the marked lines.

Table2 Conditions of the tensile test specimens.

Name of specimens	t (mm)	L (mm)	W (mm)	N
Condition of JIS	2	50	25	6
W35t2L25	2	25	35	10
W35t2L100	2	100	35	10
W35t4L25	4	25	35	10
W35t4L100	4	100	35	10

Fig.9 Results of tensile test of W35t2L25.

Table1 Elastic properties used in this study.

Elastic modulus (Fiber direction)	E_1 (GPa)	105
Elastic modulus (vertical direction)	E_2 (GPa)	4
Poisson's ratio (contraction in the vertical direction)	ν_{12}	0.3
Poisson's ratio (contraction in the fiber direction)	ν_{21}	0.01
Shear modulus	G_{12} (GPa)	1.2

Fig.10 Results of tensile test of W35t2L100.

Fig.11 Results of tensile test of W35t4L25.

Fig.14 Result of tensile test of W35t2L25 using the contact extensometer.

Fig.12 Results of tensile test of W35t4L100.

Fig.15 Comparison of the experimental results and calculated results in the average elastic modulus.

Fig.13 Tensile test using the contact extensometer.

Fig.16 Comparison of the experimental results and calculated results in the coefficient of variation.

Fig.17 Differences between the number of simulations of tensile test of W35t2L25n10.

Fig.20 Effect of the number of specimens in an experiment.

Fig.18 Relationship between the coefficient of variation and the specimen size.

Fig.21 Effect of the cut length of UD tapes.

Fig.19 Effect of the size of specimen without changes in volume.

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